

Experimental and Analytical Study of J-stiffened Composite Panels Loaded in Axial Compression

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ABSTRACT

An experimental and analytical study was conducted to determine the buckling and post-buckled behaviour of composite panels with J-shape stiffeners under compression loading. Four panels, three cocured and one secondary bonded, were tested. A shadow Moiré technique was also utilized to determine buckling deformations of the panels during tests. A finite element method was used to predict buckling and the post-buckled loads of the stiffened panels. The experimental buckling loads, as well as the failure loads were in good agreement with the analytical results. The strain data from the tests were also in close agreement with those predicted by analysis.

Keywords: Composite, Stiffened Panel, Buckling.

1. INTRODUCTION

Use of advanced composites in aircraft structures has demonstrated the potential for decreasing structural weight. Weight savings result from the high stiffness-to-density and high strength-to-density properties of fibres such as carbon. Also, weight may be saved by tailoring the ply orientations of laminated composites to meet the structural needs.

In conventional aircraft applications, it is common practice to design stiffened metallic plate and shell structures to buckle below design ultimate load. Post-buckled design allows buckling before design limit load is reached and the buckled structure can carry design ultimate load. Panels are frequently designed to carry loads that are three or four times the initial buckling load (1-10). Usually, the post-buckled design results in a significant weight saving when compared to buckle-resistant design. This paper is concerned with the analysis, fabrication and testing of composite panels with J-shape stiffeners. Predicted and experimental initial buckling and post-buckled loads of stiffened composite panels under compression loading are also presented and discussed.

2. TEST PANEL CONFIGURATION AND PREPARATION

The stiffened panel configuration consisted of a flat 12-ply skin and three equally spaced longitudinal J-shape stiffeners, having a web of 12 plies, a flange of 5 plies and a cap of 24

plies. Figure 1 shows the geometry, dimensions and stacking sequence of the panels and the detailed description can be found in (11).

The composite material used in this study was unidirectional tape of Hercules IM6 carbon fibre pre-impregnated with Narmco 5245C resin. Typical mechanical properties of this material are presented in Table 1. Three panels (J1,J2 and J3) were made using the cocuring technique, while a panel J4 was made using secondary bonding.

The panels were ultrasonically inspected using C-scan in both the pulse-echo and reflection pulse-echo modes; no significant defects were detected except for some small defects found in the web of panel J3.

The loaded ends of the panels were milled to a flatness tolerance of 0.1 mm and a parallel-end tolerance of 0.2 mm. After machining, the ends of the panels were potted into steel U-shape channels with epoxy resin. The channels acted as moulds and also served as end plates for transferring the load to the panel.

3. ANALYSIS

3.1 Modelling

The initial buckling and post-buckled loads were predicted for the panels using a commercially available finite element program (MARC) described in Reference 12. The finite element model consisted of 500 elements in total (Figure 2) of which 440 were thick shell elements with shear transfer capabilities and they had bilinear interpolation between the coordinates for the displacements and rotations (MARC element type 75). The other 60 elements were one dimensional axial load carrying type (MARC element type 9) representing the intersection between a stiffener and skin to model a filler made from strips of unidirectional tape. It was estimated the 3 fillers contributed approximately 7 % to the overall stiffness of the panel.

The model had 485 nodes which included an extra node for enforced displacement or load application. This extra node was 'tied' to the edge of the panel where the load was applied. This modelling approach ensured a correct reaction distribution during the post-buckling regime. A fully fixed boundary condition was assumed for the reaction edge and the unloaded edges were assumed to be free.

3.2 Analytical Techniques

3.2.1. Elastic Buckling Analysis

The elastic buckling load was predicted by using an eigenvalue analysis based on a perturbation of the tangent stiffness matrix. This analysis used an algorithm which included a power sweep with Gram-Schmidt ortho-normalization.

The following eigenvalue equation was used during the analysis:

$$[K]\Phi - \lambda[K_g]\Phi = 0 \quad (1)$$

where K= linear elastic stiffness matrix, Φ = eigenvectors, λ = eigenvalues
 K_g = geometric stiffness matrix

3.2.2 Nonlinear Analysis

The post-buckled loads were predicted using nonlinear analysis techniques . One technique was based on the enforcement of the displacement in the axial direction and it involved the application of load in steps. In this analysis, the height of the panel was assumed to decrease in an decrement of 0.025 mm. Over a hundred decrements were necessary to predict the failure load. Two nonlinear factors were considered: i) the large deformation effect and ii) the material properties.

The large deformation effect is a nonlinear change in the structural behavior and eventually leads to a loss in stability. In the analysis the residual load correction was used to enforce global equilibrium at the beginning of each decrement. The equation for this correction is :

$$R=P-\int \beta^t \sigma dV \quad (2)$$

Where:

R = residual load correction

P = applied load

β^t = differential operator that transforms displacement to strains

σ = generalized stresses

V = volume

A typical residual load correction curve is shown in Figure 3. The residual load correction was kept under 0.0001 of the applied load on the panel per decrement.

The material nonlinearity was modeled with a progressive failure algorithm (14) based on the maximum stress criteria. During the computation, the stress state in each ply was calculated. When the calculated stress in the fibre was higher than the maximum fibre strength, the stiffness property of the fibre was assumed to equal the stiffness property of the matrix at that particular integration point. When matrix failure was predicted, its stiffness was assumed to equal one tenth of its original value. The element stiffness matrix was then recomputed by integrating across the plies with the updated properties. This process can be expressed in the following equations:

$$\text{Fiber failure : } [E_{11}, E_{22}, G_{12}, \nu_{12}] \rightarrow [E_{22}, E_{22}, G_{12}, \nu_{12}] \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Matrix failure : } [E_{11}, E_{22}, G_{12}, \nu_{12}] \rightarrow [E_{11}, 0.1E_{22}, G_{12}, \nu_{12}] \quad (4)$$

where E_{11} = Young's modulus in the fibre direction

E_{22} = Young's modulus transverse to the fibre direction

G_{12} = In-plane shear modulus

ν_{12} = Major Poisson's ratio

4. EXPERIMENT

4.1 STRAIN AND DEFLECTION MEASUREMENT

Based on a literature survey (9), the maximum out-of-plane displacement of this type of stiffened composite panel would likely occur in the centre bay of the panel, near the midlength. Hence most of the strain gauges were bonded to the midlength area of the panel in order to capture critical strains in the buckled and post-buckled states. The selection of locations for the strain gauges was

based on the preliminary assumption that they would be on the expected peaks and valleys of the buckled skin. Also, back-to-back axial gauges were selected for all the locations, except for those on the webs, to monitor the initial buckling. The gauges located on the webs were in a shear pair configuration.

A shadow Moiré technique was utilized to determine the out-of-plane deformations (buckling patterns) of the test panels. A dial gauge was used to determine the shortening (axial deflection) of the test panel. Readings were recorded at pre-determined load levels and were plotted against the axial loads after the test. A typical load-axial displacement curve is shown in Figure 4.

4.2 TESTING

The panels were tested in an universal testing machine. The test panel was placed vertically on a flat platen, and the upper end was positioned to contact a platen connected to the test machine. The compression load was increased at a relatively constant rate until the ultimate failure of the test panel occurred. A typical test set-up is shown in Figure 5.

Strain and load outputs were gathered by a data acquisition system (Sciometric System 200) and recorded by a computer. Selected gauge outputs were monitored to verify that the load distribution in the panel was uniform. The shadow Moiré technique was used to monitor buckling patterns and any delamination during the test.

5. DISCUSSION OF PREDICTED AND TEST RESULTS

5.1 INITIAL BUCKLING LOADS

The initial buckling load was determined from the load-strain curves as the load at which either the readings from back-to-back strain gauges began to separate or the point of sudden change in the slope of the curve . The initial buckling loads were also estimated from the shadow Moiré fringe patterns and the results from both techniques agreed reasonably well. The predicted initial buckling load was 51.22 kN which was approximately 10 % below the average experimental result of 56.6 kN (4 panels), see Table 2. The average initial buckling load of the cocured panels (J1, J2 and J3) was 13.5 % greater than the predicted value , and this discrepancy could be due to the differences between the cured thicknesses and the assumed thicknesses for analysis. Panel J4 which was manufactured by secondary bonding had excellent agreement between the predicted and experimental loads.

5.2 FAILURE LOADS, STRAINS AND MODES

The three cocured panels (J1,J2, and J3) failed at a average load of 210.4 kN. The fourth panel failed at 249.1 kN, which is about 18 % higher than the cocured ones. Panel J3 failed at lowest load which was 198.7 kN. This might be attributed to the existence of some small defects which had been detected in the web during the inspection. The predicted load was 227.2 kN which was approximately 3% above the average experimental result of four panels.

The contour pattern in each bay was predicted as two contours at the initial buckling load and gradually changed to four before failure. During the testing, two contours were initially developed in each bay at an average load of 56.6 kN and then gradually evolved into five contours in each bay as the load increased except for panel J2 which exhibited only four contours. The locations of

the strain gauges bonded to the test panel are shown in Figure 6. The experimental strains from panel J2 and predicted strains for two locations are plotted against load in Figure 7 and 8, and the results are in good agreement. The predicted strain distribution in the panel at failure can be seen in Figure 9.

The failure mode was associated with compression failure of the caps, local delamination in the flange-skin intersection and failure along the 45° lines in the skin. The maximum strains measured in all the test panels were less than 0.6 % (5911 microstrain). Prior to the failure of the panel, partial separation of the flange from the skin was observed as a sudden change in the shadow Moire pattern, but it is noted that the separations (delaminations) appeared to be local in nature. The final failure loads of the panels ranged from 3.3 to 4.8 times higher than their initial buckling loads. This demonstrated that the panels performed with post-buckled capabilities.

6. CONCLUSIONS

1. Comparison of the magnitude of initial skin buckling and ultimate load indicated that the panels exhibited a good capability to carry load well beyond the onset of local buckling, i.e. good post-buckled performance.
2. Secondary bonded stiffened panels may carry slightly higher loads than cocured stiffened panels
3. The predicted and experimental initial buckling and failure loads were in good agreement.

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Table 1. Material properties (R.T.)

Mechanical Properties	
0° Tensile Modulus (GPa)	180.5
0° Compressive Modulus (GPa)	147.7
90° Tensile Modulus (GPa)	8.86
90° Compressive Modulus (GPa)	7.34
±45° Shear Modulus (GPa)	5.66
0° Tensile Poisson Ratio	0.31
0° Compressive Poisson Ratio	0.36

Table 2. Analysis and test results

Panel	Buckling Load (kN)	Failure Load (kN)	
Analysis	51.2	227.2	
J1	54.9	224.2	Co-cured
J2	63.7	208.3	Co-cured
J3	55.9	198.7	Co-cured
J4	51.9	249.1	Secondary bonding
Average	56.6 [58.1]	220.0 [210.9]	

[] = an average of J1, J2 and J3 only

Figure 3 - Residual load correction

Figure 1: Panel geometry, dimensions and stacking sequences

Figure 2 - Finite element model

Figure 4 - Typical load deflection curve

Figure 6 - Strain gauge locations

Figure 8 - Strains in stiffener cap

Figure 5: A typical test set-up

Figure 7 - Strains in skin

Figure 9 - Strain distribution at failure